

Supporting Information

Electrospinning of softwood kraft lignin with cellulose acetate: dye adsorption, carbonization and carbon dioxide capture

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Table S1. Fitting equilibrium model parameters for methylene blue adsorption on electrospun fiber mat.

Model	$Q_m \text{ mg g}^{-1}$	$K_L \text{ Lmg}^{-1}$	$K_F L^{1/n_F} \text{ mg}^{1-1/n_F} \text{ g}^{-1}$	$1/n_F$	$K_{LF} \text{ Lmg}^{-1}$	n_{LF}	R^2_{adj}
Langmuir	17.69 ± 1.5	0.92 ± 0.5					0.87
Freundlich			7.89 ± 1.6	0.19 ± 0.05			0.84
Langmuir–Freundlich	19.50 ± 4.9				0.65 ± 0.91	0.61 ± 0.38	0.87

Table S2. Benchmark comparison of CO₂ uptake performance of carbonized SKL–CA nanofibers developed in this work with previously reported lignin-derived carbon materials.

Type of lignin	Technique	Pre/post-treatment	BET surface area (m ² /g)	CO ₂ adsorption capacity (mmol/g)	Reference
Alkali lignin (Solar bio, Beijing)	Pyrolysis @750 °C, N ₂	Post treatment: Acid (10% HCl) washing assisted with ultrasound	978–1134	3.5–4.0 (25 °C)	¹
Alkali lignin (Solar bio, Beijing)	Pyrolysis @750 °C, N ₂	N/A	118	0.68 (25 °C)	¹
Alkali lignin (Solar bio, Beijing)	Negative pressure Pyrolysis @800 °C, N ₂	Post treatment: Acid (5% HCl) washing assisted with ultrasound	1577	3.6 (25 °C)	²
Alkali lignin (Solar bio, Beijing)	Negative pressure Pyrolysis @800 °C, N ₂	N/A	216	0.28 (0 °C)	²
Corn straw lignin	Pyrolysis @300–600 °C, N ₂	H ₃ PO ₄ activation	820	0.4 (0 °C)	³
Enzymatic hydrolysis lignin	Microwave @800 MW	Pretreatment: Humified N ₂ , mixed with KOH	480–2870	0.57–1.31 (30 °)	⁴
Softwood kraft lignin (BioPiva 100, Indulin AT)	Pyrolysis @600–900 °C, N ₂	Oxidative thermostabilization of particles in the presence of 2.5 wt% of CNF and physical activation using NH ₃ steam	1152	1.75 (40 °C)	⁵
Dealkaline lignin (TCI America)	Pyrolysis @800 °C, N ₂	Pretreatment: Grinded with Na ₂ S ₂ O ₃ and KOH	741–3626	0.75–10 (25 °C)	⁶
Enzymatic hydrolysis lignin	Mechanochemical treatment and low-temperature activation @600 °C	Pretreatment: Mixed with Melamine/Ultrasonication/Hydrothermal treatment; Post treatment: Washed with HCl	602–2030	3.26–5.0 (0 °C)	⁷
Softwood kraft lignin (UPM BioPiva 100)	Pyrolysis @800 °C, N ₂	Pretreatment: Mixed with urea and HNO ₃	1000	1.4 (20 °C)	⁸
Softwood kraft lignin (UPM BioPiva 100)	Pyrolysis @1000 °C, N ₂	Electrospinning with cellulose acetate, Oxidative thermostabilization	33–781	3.1–3.9 (0 °C)	This work

Figure S1. X-Ray diffractogram (a) pristine CA and SKL and (b) thermostabilized SKL–CA nanofibers with different composition in wt.%, Thermogram of (c) pristine CA and SKL in air, (d) SKL–CA nanofibers with different composition in wt.% in air and (e) Thermogram of thermostabilized SKL–CA nanofibers with different composition in wt.% in inert atmosphere.

Figure S2. Digital image of spent fibers (SKL:CA 80:20) (a) before, (b) after carbonization, SEM images of (c) thermostabilized, (d) carbonized spent fibers and (e) EDS mapping of carbonized spent fibers (SKL:CA 80:20). Scale bar in the panel (e) is same for all the EDS mapping given.

Figure S3. Digital images of the thermostabilized (left) and carbonized (right) SKL-CA nanofibers with composition in wt.% (a) 0:100, (b) 50:50, (c) 60:40, (d) 70:30 and (e) 80:20 respectively.

Figure S4. Scanning electron microscopic images of thermostabilized SKL-CA nanofibers with composition (a)–(d) 70:30 wt.%, at different magnifications.

Figure S5. Scanning electron microscopic images of thermostabilized SKL-CA nanofibers with composition (a)–(d) 80:20 wt.% at different magnifications.

Figure S6. Scanning electron microscopic images of thermostabilized SKL-CA nanofibers with composition (a) 50:50 wt.% and (b) 60:40 wt.%.

Figure S7. Scanning electron microscopic images of thermostabilized (a) and (b) carbonized CA nanofibers (SKL 0).

Figure S8. (a)–(d) Additional Scanning electron microscopic images and (e) EDS Mapping of carbonized SKL-CA nanofibers with 50:50 composition in wt.% (SKL 50). Scale bar in the panel (e) is same for all the EDS mapping given.

Figure S9. (a)–(d) Additional Scanning electron microscopic images and (e) EDS Mapping of carbonized SKL-CA nanofibers with 60:40 composition in wt.% (SKL 60). Scale bar in the panel (e) is same for all the EDS mapping given.

Figure S10. (a)–(d) Additional Scanning electron microscopic images and (e) EDS Mapping of carbonized SKL–CA nanofibers with 70:30 composition in wt.% (SKL 70). Scale bar in the panel (e) is same for all the EDS mapping given.

Figure S11. (a)–(d) Additional Scanning electron microscopic images and (e) EDS Mapping of carbonized SKL–CA nanofibers with 80:20 composition in wt.% (SKL 80). Scale bar in the panel (e) is same for all the EDS mapping given.

Figure S12. (a)–(e) Deconvoluted Raman spectra with Gaussian fit corresponding to **Fig. 7b**.

Figure S13. Solid-state ^{13}C MAS spectrum of carbonized SKL-CA nanofibers with 80:20 composition in wt.% (SKL 80).

References:

1. Cao, W. *et al.* Novel post-treatment of ultrasound assisting with acid washing enhance lignin-based biochar for CO₂ capture : Adsorption performance and mechanism. *Chem. Eng. J.* **471**, 144523 (2023).
2. Pan, Z. *et al.* Lignin-based hierarchical porous biochar prepared from negative pressure pyrolysis enhanced CO₂ and VOCs adsorption. *Sep. Purif. Technol.* **345**, 127398 (2024).
3. Sun, Y., Yang, G., Zhang, J., Wang, Y. & Yao, M. Activated Carbon Preparation from Lignin by H₃PO₄ Activation and Its Application to Gas Separation. *Chem. Eng. Technol.* **35**, 309–316 (2012).
4. Chen, W., Wang, X., Hashisho, Z., Feizbakhshan, M. & Shariaty, P. Template-free and fast one-step synthesis from enzymatic hydrolysis lignin to hierarchical porous carbon for CO₂ capture. *Microporous Mesoporous Mater.* **280**, 57–65 (2019).
5. Zhao, B. *et al.* Lignin-Based Porous Supraparticles for Carbon Capture. *ACS Nano* **15**, 6774–6786 (2021).
6. Saha, D. *et al.* CO₂ capture in lignin-derived and nitrogen-doped hierarchical porous carbons. *Carbon N. Y.* **121**, 257–266 (2017).
7. Liu, D. *et al.* Insights into mechanochemical assisted preparation of lignin-based N-doped porous carbon with tunable porosity and ultrahigh surface oxygen content for efficient CO₂ capture. *Sep. Purif. Technol.* **347**, 127657 (2024).
8. Tkachenko, O. *et al.* Kraft Lignin-Derived Microporous Nitrogen-Doped Carbon Adsorbent for Air and Water Purification. *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* **16**, 3427–3441 (2024).